

International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology (IJCSIT)

ISSN : 0975 - 3826 (Online) ; 0975 - 4660 (Print)

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SCOPE OF THE JOURNAL

The AIRCC's **International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology (IJCSIT)** is devoted to fields of Computer Science and Information Systems. The IJCSIT is a peer-reviewed scientific journal published in electronic form as well as print form. The mission of this journal is to publish original contributions in its field in order to propagate knowledge amongst its readers and to be a reference publication.

IJCSIT publishes original research papers and review papers, as well as auxiliary material such as: research papers, case studies, technical reports etc.

Topics of Interest

- Algorithms and Bioinformatics
- Computer Architecture and Real Time Systems
- Database and Data Mining
- Dependable, Reliable and Autonomic Computing
- Distributed and Parallel Systems & Algorithms
- DSP/Image Processing/Pattern Recognition/Multimedia
- Embedded System and Software
- Game and Software Engineering
- Geographical Information Systems/ Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GIS/GNSS)
- Grid and Scalable Computing
- Intelligent Information & Database Systems
- IT policy and Business Management
- Mobile and Ubiquitous Computing
- Modeling and Simulation
- Multimedia Systems and Services
- Networking and Communications
- Parallel and Distributed Systems
- Security and Information Assurance
- Soft Computing (AI, Neural Networks, Fuzzy Systems, etc.)
- Software Engineering
- Web and Internet Computing
- Blockchain
- Data Mining
- Deep Learning
- Big Data
- Internet of Things
- Machine Learning & Applications
- NLP

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2. Accept with minor changes
3. weak Accept with major changes
4. Reject

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Bibliographic Information

ISSN : 0975 - 4660
e-ISSN : 0975 - 3826
doi : 10.5121/ijcsit

<https://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit.html>

International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)

Google Scholar Indexing

H –Index – 50, Citations 9527, i10-Index 230

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World Journal Clout Index (WJCI)

Impact Factor

2019- 0.115

2020- 0.242

WJCI 2019

Year: 2019

WJCI Certificate

Journal Title	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY				
Country/Region	India				
ISSNS	0975-4660/0975-3826				
Publisher/Sponsor	A I R C C Publishing Corporation				
Total Cites	163				
Impact Factor	0.115				
Discipline Impact	Discipline	WJCI	Rank	Quartile	WJCI Percentile
	Computer Science and Technology General	0.380	137/172	Q4	20.35
	Average Value	0.380	—	—	20.35

WJCI 2020

Year: 2020

WJCI Certificate

Journal Title	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY				
Country/Region	India				
ISSN	0975-4660/0975-5826				
Publisher/Sponsor	AIRCC Publishing Corporation				
Total Cites	435				
Impact Factor	0.242				
Discipline Impact	Discipline	WJCI	Rank	Quartile	WJCI Percentile
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World Journal Clout Index (WJCI) $WJCI = WAJCI + WI = 0.486 + 0.225 = 0.711$